

EXCELERATE Deliverable [13.1]

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WP No.	13	
Lead Beneficiary:	ELIXIR Hub	
WP Title	Communications, Industry and Community Engagement	
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WP leader:	Andrew Smith	1 ELIXIR Hub
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1. Executive Summary

One of the major priorities of WP13, and a critical factor in the overall effectiveness of EXCELERATE, is the development of an ELIXIR-wide Communications Strategy and the effective implementation of this. The scale of users of ELIXIR's services across the globe, as well as the number of partners involved in jointly running the infrastructure, requires that ELIXIR uses modern, effective communication channels to convey simple, clear messages. This Deliverable saw the development of ELIXIR's first, infrastructure-wide Communications Strategy. The strategy has undergone several rounds of consultation with internal partners and Communications experts across the ELIXIR Nodes (see task 1.2), including during a one-day workshop help to gather stakeholder input. The completed Strategy has been endorsed by ELIXIR Heads of Nodes and will remain a living document, undergoing regular review and updates as required.

The Communications Strategy sets the overall strategic direction for dissemination activities led by the ELIXIR Hub and Nodes. It sets out the various priorities and procedures to be followed across all aspects of ELIXIR's communications, from internal project communication to external communication with users. It includes recommendations for scientific communication, social media, web-based resources, video and printed materials. The Communications Strategy deliverable links directly to **Task 13.1: Develop a coordinated and user-centric Communications presence for ELIXIR (16PM)**, and through defining ELIXIR's Communication's and community engagement priorities, also indirectly supports the implementation of other tasks including: Subtask 13.1.3: Develop suite of high-quality communications materials; and Subtask 13.3.1. ELIXIR representation at key scientific events and conferences (3PM).

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

[this section is completed by project management]

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Develop a coordinated and user-centric Communications presence for ELIXIR. (Task 13.1)		x
2	Support innovation and usage of ELIXIR from Europe's life-science industries and SMEs. (Task 13.2)		x
3	Create specific outreach channels to key user communities. (Task 13.3)	x	
4	Engage potential members across the globe. (Task 13.4)	x	

3. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

4. Adjustments made

The deliverable is slightly delayed because the development of the Strategy required several thorough rounds of consultation from ELIXIR's many stakeholders and bodies.

Background information

[this section is completed by project management]

Background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	13	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Communications, Industry and Community Engagement		
Lead	Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)		
Participant number and person months per participant			
1 – EMBL 36			
<p>The overall aim of WP13 is to ensure that a maximum number of scientists and companies are aware of ELIXIR's services, developments, opportunities and events. Reaching out to specific communities, including industry and SMEs, will allow ELIXIR to understand user's needs better, ensuring that the most effective services are developed.</p>			
<p>Objectives</p> <p>This will be achieved by carrying out tasks that address four, complementary objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a coordinated and user-centric Communications presence for ELIXIR. (Task 13.1) • Support innovation and usage of ELIXIR from Europe's life-science industries and SMEs. (Task 13.2) • Create specific outreach channels to key user communities. (Task 13.3) • Engage potential members across the globe. (Task 13.4) <p>WP13 will build upon many existing communications resources and channels. The main ELIXIR-Europe website, for example, will house the project website and existing ELIXIR stakeholder mailing lists will help ensure that outcomes from the project are disseminated widely. WP13 will focus on enhancing these existing platforms and optimising them to ensure maximum impact from a relatively modest WP budget.</p> <p>Work Package Lead: Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)</p> <p>It is estimated by the EC that there are around 500,000 life scientists in the EU alone⁶³. The fundamental importance of data-driven research in the life sciences means that</p>			

many of these scientists are potential users of ELIXIR's services. ELIXIR likely has largest user community of any ESFRI Research Infrastructure. Furthermore, ELIXIR's Preparatory Phase report⁶⁴ highlighted the range of users supported, including: bioinformaticians and computational biologists; bench scientists; biologists; geneticists; biochemists; clinical specialists; and plant, environmental and marine scientists. In addition, industry is a major user of ELIXIR resources from Pharmaceutical and Biotech industries through to crop science and aquaculture companies and SMEs.

Unlike many physical or single-sited infrastructures, where operators can build face to face dialogue with a small number of users, ELIXIR is an Open Data infrastructure where millions users access services via web interfaces. It is vital to create the effective communications and outreach mechanisms to interact with these users in a manner that is effective for users and efficient for ELIXIR partners.

Task 13.1: Develop a coordinated and user-centric Communications presence for ELIXIR

The scale of users across the globe requires that ELIXIR uses modern, effective tools to communicate its scientific and operational messages. The distributed nature of ELIXIR, with over 100 institutes involved, also requires that there is a consistency and clarity of messaging between partners. Task 1 comprises three Sub-tasks that will collectively ensure that the internal processes are in place so that ELIXIR can present a single, coordinated interface to its users and that effective communications materials are developed.

Subtask 13.1.1: Develop and implement an ELIXIR-wide Communications Strategy

The ELIXIR Communications Strategy will set the overall strategic direction for ELIXIR's dissemination activities to users in academia, industry policy-makers and funders. The strategy will include scientific communication, social media, web-based resources, newsletters, video and printed materials. It will be reviewed and updated annually to take into account new technologies and developments. Owned by the ELIXIR Hub, it will be developed jointly by the emerging Communication Expert group (Task 13.1.2) and other key strategic bodies, most notably the ELIXIR Heads of Nodes committee and the Work Package leads of ELIXIR-EXCELERATE. It will identify the key scientific conferences that ELIXIR should attend and the suite of materials that will be produced to reach out to user groups (Task 13.1.3). It will also harness the existing social media channels run by ELIXIR Nodes, and build on the distribution channels created during ELIXIR's Preparatory and interim phases.

Subtask 13.1.2: Create and operate an ELIXIR Communications Expert group

In order to implement the most effective Communications Strategy, a tightly-coordinated network of communications and outreach experts from ELIXIR Nodes is required. Harnessing the local communication channels that ELIXIR Nodes already have with their own respective national bioinformatics communities will provide efficiencies of scale at the European-level. We will create an information exchange network of Node experts that adopts the latest software and web-based applications. Annual face-to-face meetings of all Communications experts and bilateral meetings between members will be critical to cement relationships within the network, and will be supplemented by video/telephone conferencing and use of the ELIXIR intranet (WP12).

Subtask 13.1.3 Develop suite of high-quality communications materials

To effectively communicate ELIXIR's services to various stakeholder communities, a suite of high-quality promotional materials will be produced. A short ELIXIR video will feature interviews with scientists and industry users and will set out the structure of ELIXIR, the range of services offered and how these can be accessed. Printed materials, posters and banners will be printed and distributed to all ELIXIR Nodes to support their local dissemination activities. Annual scientific reports will capture the scientific and operational output of ELIXIR- EXCELERATE.

Additional resources required: Video and printed materials subcontracting costs €45,000

Task 13.2: Support innovation and usage of ELIXIR by Europe's life-science industries and SMEs

Industrial use of Europe's bioinformatics resources is high. These industries are major employers globally, generating wealth and supporting transformation to a knowledge-based economy.

Industry sees added value in ELIXIR65 in terms of reduced costs and decreased duplication of effort for them, higher scalability, access to common data and interface standards and much better public-private data integration. Many of these requirements will be addressed by the general implementation of ELIXIR and are as relevant for academia as for industry. Additionally, Task 13.2 will ensure that industry and SMEs are offered direct, bespoke support and engagement.

Subtask 13.2.1: Build lasting partnerships with industry initiatives, bodies and SME associations

In order to understand the needs of Europe's industry and SME sector, it is necessary to forge close links with industry and SME association bodies, particularly EFPIA, local EENs, the European Biotechnology Network, the BioBasedIndustries Consortium and regional bioclusters. A scoping exercise and face-to-face meetings will map these organisations and establish dissemination channels. This will ensure that a maximum number of companies are aware of ELIXIR's services and that the content of ELIXIR's Innovation and SME programme (Task 13.2.2) is relevant to the needs of Europe's SMEs. The Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI) - and many of its current projects - is considered as a priority for closer engagement. ELIXIR will seek to conclude formal collaboration agreements with key IMI projects such as OpenPHACTS.

Subtask 13.2.2: Expand the reach and impact of ELIXIR's Innovation and SME programme

Expanding ELIXIR's emerging Innovation and SME programme66 will allow partners to disseminate the results, services, tools and outcomes to a large number of companies across Europe. Building on a successful start to this programme, we will fund 8 dedicated events across the duration of the project. With around 50 delegates attending each event, hundreds of Europe's SMEs will be directly supported across the duration of the grant. Individual events will be themed to address the outcomes from ELIXIR-EXCELERATE Use Cases (WPs 6 to 9) so will include health and rare diseases, marine sciences and plant sciences. We will work through the key bioclusters and industry organisations identified within Task 13.2.1.

Additional resources required: €120,000 for Innovation and SME events (€15,000 per event)

Task 13.3: Create specific outreach channels across the globe to key user

communities and potential member states

No infrastructure is effective over the long-term unless it offers services that meet the needs of users. The Preparatory Phase showed that ELIXIR is perhaps unique in the size and variety of its respective user communities. Task 13.3.1 will ensure that ELIXIR engages effectively with users through attendance at scientific conferences. Task and 13.3.2 will allow ELIXIR to forge lasting relations with the key bioinformatics community-driven initiatives such as GOBLET for training and proteomics standards initiatives.

In addition, for ELIXIR to realise its potential on the world stage and drive global bioinformatics collaboration, regular interaction, and ultimately direct membership from countries outside Europe, is required. Equally, collaboration with other major global data initiatives is necessary. Task 13.3.3 will ensure that ELIXIR works strategically with key countries outside Europe and the major international infrastructure initiatives that are of relevance.

Subtask 13.3.1. ELIXIR representation at key scientific events and conferences

Scientific conferences provide an effective way of communicating ELIXIR's services to its large and diverse user base. ELIXIR will attend, display booths and run tech track sessions at a number of key scientific conferences within Europe and beyond.

Conference participation will focus primarily on showcasing ELIXIR to scientific conferences at which ELIXIR's users attend. However, some conferences will have policy-makers and funders as the target audience. The exact conferences to attend will be defined in the ELIXIR Communication's Strategy but major events are summarised in Part B section 2.2.5.

Additional resources required: Conference costs of €60,000

Subtask 13.3.2: Forge lasting relations with bioinformatics community initiatives

In the life sciences, many users, developers and operators that share a common interest are organised into 'communities'. Many of these are very well established taking the form of initiatives, networks, societies or consortia. I.e. the "HUPO Proteomics Standards Initiative" for the development of standards in proteomics. Such communities provide fora for knowledge exchange and collaboration and platforms for driving common agreements and community development. ELIXIR recognises the contribution of these and will interact with them strategically. We will not duplicate their efforts but rather engage with them to support and promote their, adding value at the European level. This Task will ensure that ELIXIR identifies and collaborates with the key initiatives.

Task 13.4: Develop ELIXIR's International strategy

ELIXIR is considered by the G20 countries to be of global significance and with great potential for membership by countries outside of Europe. Task 13.4 will facilitate the process of countries joining ELIXIR as members, thus addressing the Call requirement of increasing membership.

The International Strategy will have a two-fold purpose: 1) support the membership of countries outside of Europe, particularly G20 countries; 2) and foster collaboration between ELIXIR and global science initiatives, such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health and INCF. The International Strategy will primarily serve as an internal document and will be subject to annual updates following review by ELIXIR Board and the SAB.

5. Appendix 1: ELIXIR Communications Strategy

ELIXIR Communications strategy

Date	Editor	Changes
2 June 2016	Premysl Velek	Version 1 (Initial version)

Next review date: 2 November 2016

Contact:

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1. Introduction

This document sets out a communications strategy for ELIXIR. Its objective is to act as the reference point for all aspects of ELIXIR's communications, providing guidelines to partners internally, and harmonising communications to users externally.

This document is intended for members of ELIXIR who need a comprehensive overview of ELIXIR communications channels and policies. The Annexes provide more detailed guidance on specific aspects of ELIXIR communications and are directed to ELIXIR community members responsible for communications (Communications officers, Events officer, Community managers, etc.) working in ELIXIR Nodes or in ELIXIR services.

The strategy maps out ELIXIR's target audiences, defines key messages and sets out the main objectives, deliverables and tools that will be used for implementation. The structure of the strategy follows the typical communications workflow: from establishing objectives and defining target audiences, to specific communication tools, timeline and evaluation:

- Objectives
- Audiences
- Messages
- Tools and activities
- Synergy
- Timeline / action plan
- Evaluation

The document has been developed following consultation with ELIXIR stakeholders: the key topics were discussed during the Communications strategy workshop, held in Cambridge in December 2015; the wider ELIXIR community was also consulted through online survey conducted in October-November 2015.

The Technical Coordinators Group discussed promoting ELIXIR services and proposed a number of measures. [Annex VII: Promoting ELIXIR services](#) summarises the outcomes of the discussion.

The initial version of the document was consulted with ELIXIR Communications experts group, with ELIXIR Heads of Nodes, and with ELIXIR Training and Technical Coordinators.

2. ELIXIR communications architecture

The ELIXIR communications architecture translates ELIXIR's objectives defined in the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2014-2018 into a set of clear and actionable messages. The mission statement and tagline form the basis of the architecture, communicating ELIXIR's purpose and *raison d'être*. The mission statement is developed into a set of key messages that aim at a specific audience and demonstrate concretely how ELIXIR fulfils its mission.

The communication architecture as a whole define:

- The purpose of ELIXIR
- What ELIXIR does
- For whom
- Benefits of ELIXIR to its users
- Impact of ELIXIR

Mission statement

A mission statement communicates the purpose of an organisation - it is a concise and simple statement defining why the organisation exists and what its goals are:

ELIXIR's mission statement is:

ELIXIR is building a sustainable European infrastructure for biological information, supporting life science research and its translation to: Medicine; Environment; the Bioindustries; and Society.

Tagline

ELIXIR's mission statement lead to a tagline that forms part of ELIXIR's visual identity:

Coordinating access to a sustainable portfolio of life-science data services in Europe

Slogan

The slogan is:

Data for Life

This tagline will be retained for use on banners and merchandise such as t-shirts, stickers etc.

Boilerplate

Boilerplate text provides the essential details about ELIXIR, its objectives. It comprises standard text describing what ELIXIR is and does, and should be used whenever it is needed to present ELIXIR in a concise way (in press releases, job adverts, grant applications, event invitations etc.)

ELIXIR's boilerplate text is:

ELIXIR unites Europe's leading life-science organisations in managing and safeguarding the massive amounts of data being generated in publicly funded research. It coordinates, integrates and sustains bioinformatics resources across its Member States and enables users in academia and industry to access vital data, tools, standards, computational and training services for their research.

Key messages

ELIXIR key messages communicate the organisation's mission and objectives and demonstrate how they are connected to the organisation's activities and target audiences.

Key messages - aligned with ELIXIR Scientific Programme and strategic objectives¹ - build on the mission statement and provide examples of how the organisation's target groups (see below) can benefit from it. They are tailored to each specific target group and respond to common questions ELIXIR users have.

Table 1: ELIXIR key messages

Key message	Target audience
ELIXIR simplifies access to quality-controlled data, services and tools for researchers working in all life-science disciplines (Strategic Objective No. 4)	Bioinformaticians Life scientists
ELIXIR enables life science researchers to make the most of the rapidly growing life science data (Strategic Objective No. 1)	
ELIXIR ensures long-term sustainability of Europe's core life science data resources (Strategic Objective No. 2)	
ELIXIR facilitates open access and open science in the life science research	
ELIXIR empowers ELIXIR Member States to integrate life-science data and services and maximise their bioinformatics expertise ELIXIR consolidates Europe's national centres, services, and core bioinformatics resources into a single, coordinated infrastructure. (Strategic Objective No. 1)	ELIXIR consortium (organisations and individuals in ELIXIR Nodes) Research funders
ELIXIR trains life science researchers to effectively exploit the data, tools, standards and compute infrastructure offered by ELIXIR.	Bioinformaticians Life scientists

¹ ELIXIR Strategic Objectives 2014-2018, ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2014-2018, p.10-13, https://www.elixir-europe.org/sites/default/files/documents/elixir_scientific_programme_o.pdf

(Strategic objective No 7.)	
ELIXIR supports open innovation in 'big-data' biology	Research funders Industry
ELIXIR supports Europe's bioindustries and collaboration between industry and academia	
ELIXIR helps maximising return on investment in public life-science data infrastructure	
(Strategic objective No 8.)	

3. Target audience

ELIXIR has a number of key stakeholders, essential for its mission and objectives:

- Bioinformaticians
- Life scientists
- ELIXIR consortium (organisations and individuals in ELIXIR Nodes)
- Research funders
- Industry
- Collaborators: ie ESFRI Research Infrastructures, global partners (e.g. BD2K, GOBLET) and other initiatives (e.g. GA4GH, Research Data Alliance)

These target groups are defined based on what aspect of ELIXIR activities they can benefit from². The Communications strategy workshop identified the activities and unique benefits of ELIXIR to each of the target audiences; Table 2: Benefits of ELIXIR to its target audiences. Table 2 summarises these benefits to each of the target groups and outlines messaging for them. The definition and objectives for each of the target audiences are based on the User research project commissioned by ELIXIR in 2014³. The user personas developed as part of the research are available at: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-user-research-final-research-report> .

² The ELIXIR User research project categorises bioinformaticians and life science researchers as ELIXIR users. ELIXIR users are then split up into four categories: High volume data generators, SME/industry bioinformaticians, Data providers, and Bioinformaticians.

³ Industry engagement in ELIXIR is set out in the ELIXIR Industry strategy, available at: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/system/files/industry-strategy.pdf>

Table 2: Benefits of ELIXIR to its target audiences

Target audiences	Definition	Objectives
Bioinformaticians	Experts in the field of bioinformatics: (1) Developers working on algorithms, the development aspects and the maintenance of bioinformatics tools, and (2) curators and operators who design and maintain data resources ⁴	To foster understanding of ELIXIR's role as bioinformatics research infrastructure. Ensure bioinformaticians can find and use ELIXIR services easily.
Life scientists	Generalist users of bioinformatics research infrastructure. Typically those generating data but without specific expertise or training in bioinformatics	To promote ELIXIR infrastructure tools and services To promote ELIXIR bioinformatics training resources
ELIXIR Consortium	(1) Bioinformaticians, service operators, and developers directly involved in ELIXIR, (2) National bioinformatics communities in ELIXIR Nodes	To inform about latest developments in ELIXIR and facilitate communications and information exchange between various parts of ELIXIR (ELIXIR Nodes, ELIXIR Platforms and Use Cases)
Industry and SMEs	Representatives of industry and SMEs using or interested in using ELIXIR services	To promote ELIXIR bioinformatics services and tools relevant to industry To foster dialogue between ELIXIR partners and industry users
Research funders	(1) Governments and their advisors, including national funding agencies, (2) European Commission and EU advisory and research funding bodies.	Maintain support for ELIXIR through demonstrating impact and long-term sustainability
Collaborators	Projects and key initiatives in life-sciences or other disciplines with which ELIXIR partners closely collaborates	Maintain awareness of ELIXIR and ensure the infrastructure is seen as natural and trusted partner for collaboration

⁴ Vincent A. T, Charette S. J. 2015, Who qualifies to be a bioinformatician? *Frontiers in Genetics* 6, 2015, doi: [10.3389/fgene.2015.00164](https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2015.00164)

Potential risks

The Communications Strategy workshop also identified potential risks in communicating ELIXIR to its target audiences and how they may be addressed:

Risks: ELIXIR should not be perceived as a club - a closed group that doesn't involve and collaborate with researchers from the outside

Mitigation: Communications to the target audience must include concrete examples of how users can get involved in ELIXIR or benefit from its services

Risk: ELIXIR should not be perceived as a funding agency

Mitigation: The financial benefits of ELIXIR for individual researchers or groups should not feature in ELIXIR communications. The value of ELIXIR extends beyond financial support of individual bioinformatics projects. All ELIXIR activities contribute towards ELIXIR's goal of building coherent infrastructure for life science data, and the value of each individual project and activity should be evaluated in this context.

ELIXIR serves as a know-how and knowledge resource across its Members and the European life-science community

4. ELIXIR's communication channels - overview

ELIXIR has several communications channels, often directed towards different audiences. Each channel has also its specific characteristics and requires different content and style.

Table 4 provides overview of the communications channels currently used by ELIXIR. It includes all channels managed by the ELIXIR Hub and selected channels by the ELIXIR Nodes. Each channel is then described in detail in a separate section.

Table 3: ELIXIR Communications channels

Activity	Channel	Target group
Internal communications channels		
Internal newsletter	ELIXIR Weekly brief	ELIXIR Consortium
Intranet	https://www.elixir-europe.org/intranet	ELIXIR Consortium
Mailing lists	ELIXIR mailing lists	ELIXIR Consortium
External communications channels		
Website	Main ELIXIR website: www.elixir-europe.org	All
Social media	1- Twitter 2- LinkedIn	Bioinformaticians, Life scientists, ELIXIR Consortium
External newsletter	Informed - ELIXIR quarterly Newsletter	Bioinformaticians, Life scientists, Research funders, Collaborators
Industry newsletter	Industry update	Industry
Publications	1- Scientific journals 1.a - ELIXIR F1000Research Gateway 2 - Other Publication platforms	Bioinformaticians, Research funders, Collaborators, ELIXIR Consortium
Print materials	1- Annual Reports, Scientific programme, 2- Brochures	Bioinformaticians, Life scientists, Research funders, Industry
Events	1- Events organised by ELIXIR 2- ELIXIR presentation at third party events (Conferences, workshops)	Bioinformaticians, Life scientists, Industry, ELIXIR Consortium
Videos	1- Recordings from ELIXIR webinar 2- ELIXIR Corporate video (planned for summer 2016)	Bioinformaticians, Life scientists, Research funders

Media / press	1- Press releases 2- Press invitations	Life scientists, Industry, Research funders
Communications assets		
Graphic design	1- Logo and branding 2- Illustrations	
Presentations	1- ELIXIR slide deck 2- Posters	
Others	1- ELIXIR banners 2- Giveaways / Merchandise	

ELIXIR website

The primary communications channel for ELIXIR is the main website, www.elixir-europe.org. The website will provide comprehensive information about all activities in ELIXIR. The three primary goals of the website are to inform users:

1. What ELIXIR is, what are ELIXIR activities, and how it is organised;
2. What ELIXIR offers to its stakeholders (tools, resources, training, technical activities, industry initiatives and other) and how they can benefit from them;
3. ELIXIR's future plans and objectives and how ELIXIR commits its funding.

The individual components of the website (layout, structure, accessibility, privacy) will be defined in the Website strategy (currently under development.).

Website content

The ELIXIR Hub has full editorial control over the content published on ELIXIR website. However, in developing new content, ELIXIR Hub will consult ELIXIR Platforms and Use Cases and other relevant groups within ELIXIR. A new function will allow platform members to directly contribute to the content of the website (write news, events, and suggest additions to other section of the website).

The editorial guidelines and writing style are part of the [ELIXIR Style guide \(Annex VII.\)](#).

Websites of ELIXIR Nodes

As a distributed organisation, ELIXIR's online presence is not limited to the main ELIXIR website administered by the ELIXIR Hub. Many ELIXIR Nodes have developed or are planning to develop a dedicated local website (ELIXIR Portugal, ELIXIR Norway); other Nodes present information on ELIXIR via their institutional websites (EMBL-EBI, SIB, DTL).

ELIXIR Theme

The ELIXIR Hub has developed a dedicated theme for ELIXIR and an out-of-the-box Drupal installation of it. The theme is maintained and regularly updated by the Hub, and is offered to the Nodes, together with a limited technical support.

Contact ELIXIR's web developer Martin Cook for more information: martin.cook@elixir-europe.org

Table 4: ELIXIR Nodes' websites

ELIXIR Node	URL	Comment
Belgium		
Czech Republic	https://www.elixir-czech.org	Dedicated Node website
Denmark	http://www.elixir-denmark.org	Dedicated Node website
EMBL-EBI	http://www.ebi.ac.uk	Institutional website
Estonia		
Finland	http://www.elixir-finland.org	Institutional website
France	http://www.france-bioinformatique.fr	Institutional website
Israel		
Italy		
Netherlands	http://dtls.nl	Institutional website
Norway	http://elixir-norway.org	Dedicated Node website
Portugal	http://elixir-portugal.org	Dedicated Node website
Slovenia	http://cfgbc.mf.uni-lj.si/elixir	Institutional website
Spain	http://www.inab.org	Institutional website
Sweden	http://nbis.se	Institutional website
Switzerland	http://sib.swiss	Institutional website
UK	http://elixir-uk.org	Dedicated Node website

ELIXIR services with a dedicated website:

Service	URL	Comment
TeSS portal	https://tess.elixir-uk.org	ELIXIR UK
ELIXIR Tools and Service registry (bio.tools)	http://bio.tools	ELIXIR Denmark

To maintain the ELIXIR brand and ensure consistency, there are some minimal requirements in terms of design and content for ELIXIR Nodes' websites and webpages presenting ELIXIR.

Minimal requirements for a ELIXIR Node website or webpage presenting ELIXIR:

Design	
Logo	Only official logos defined in the ELIXIR Branding guidelines (Annex V.) should be used. No alteration in colour or style is allowed.
Colours	For dedicated ELIXIR websites, the colours should be based on the ELIXIR colours defined in the Branding guidelines.
Language	All ELIXIR websites should be in English. If another language is used, an English version should be available.
Devices	The design should be optimised for mobile devices

Content	
About section	Boilerplate text (see chapter 2.1 Messages)
Contact information	Contact details to the ELIXIR Node and link to the ELIXIR Hub website
ELIXIR News feed (recommended when relevant)	ELIXIR News feed: https://www.elixir-europe.org/feeds/news.xml

Social media strategy

In addition to promoting specific ELIXIR activities and driving more visitors to the ELIXIR website, ELIXIR's social media strategy focuses on community building and networking. The emphasis is on interaction with and dialogue between ELIXIR and its main stakeholders and on engaging and reaching out to new users.

The main social media platform is Twitter, which is complemented by an ELIXIR LinkedIn account to target specific, clearly defined audiences and/or content (e.g. LinkedIn discussions to target and engage industry and to advertise job vacancies).

Twitter

ELIXIR's Twitter account is at <https://twitter.com/ELIXIREurope>. In addition to this official account maintained by the ELIXIR Hub, ELIXIR Nodes and members of the ELIXIR community use their own accounts to promote and inform stakeholders about ELIXIR. The following best practice recommendations will ensure that ELIXIR's presence on Twitter is coordinated and effective. The following guidelines provide advice to individuals and institutions how to effectively support ELIXIR on social media.

The goals of ELIXIR's Twitter presence are to:

- Build a strong base of engaged followers
- Drive more traffic to ELIXIR website
- Engage with user communities
- Monitor and improve ELIXIR's reputation
- Answer queries from the community

Guidelines to using twitter in ELIXIR communications are provided in [Annex III: ELIXIR Social Media Guidelines](#)

LinkedIn

ELIXIR LinkedIn page is at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/elixir-europe>. ELIXIR uses LinkedIn primarily to provide updates on industry activities and to post ELIXIR vacancies. Any Member of the ELIXIR community is encouraged to follow the ELIXIR page and share, like and comment on the individual posts.

Newsletters

ELIXIR weekly brief - 'All at Nodes' internal newsletter

The ELIXIR weekly brief is sent out to all members of the ELIXIR community, usually on Monday. It contains information about recent activities in the Hub, in ELIXIR Nodes and in ELIXIR Platforms and Use Cases. The goal of this weekly update is to keep partners updated about ELIXIR's activities and events at any given time: the newsletter presents an overview of ELIXIR's activities in the form of short - tweet-line news and provides links to more detailed information.

The closed mailing list includes all individuals named on ELIXIR Node applications, grants held in the name of ELIXIR and those involved in Hub-funded activities such as Implementation Studies. The mailing list currently has over 500 subscriptions; new subscribers are only added upon request from Head of Nodes, or Platform and Use Case leaders.

ELIXIR Nodes are encouraged to send information about their national activities and events. The ELIXIR Weekly brief publishes all information from the national Nodes relevant to ELIXIR, namely:

- Job vacancies in ELIXIR Nodes directly related to ELIXIR
- Information about new staff members
- Information about national and international conferences organised by ELIXIR Nodes
- Information about national workshops and other events

ELIXIR Nodes should submit their news items via email at: info@elixir-europe.org. The submission should contain (1) a short text to be included directly in the newsletter, and (2) a link to a document (website, pdf, slides) with more information.

The Dutch Techcentre for Life Science (DTL, ELIXIR Netherlands) is seeking **two Software Engineers - Linked Data**.

SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics is seeking a **Communications Manager, project manager** and **Clinical Bioinformatics Project Manager** to join their team.

Denmark hosting **1st European Conference for Translational Bioinformatics in Copenhagen, 26-27 April 2016**. ELIXIR Director, Niklas Blomberg will be one of the speakers.

ELIXIR UK and FAIRDOM jointly hosted an **ELIXIR-EXCELERATE Samples Club BYOD workshop** on 21-23 March 2016 in Manchester, UK.

Registration is now open for the next **Technical Hackathon: Tools, Workflows and Workbenches** taking place in Paris, France, 18-20 May 2016.

Image 1: Examples of news from ELIXIR Nodes

The following performance indicators will be regularly monitored to measure the success of the internal newsletter:

- Open rate - the number of subscribers who open the newsletter / number of all subscribers
- Click-through rate - the number of subscribers who click on any of the links in the newsletter / number of all subscribers

The performance of the newsletter will be reviewed on a yearly basis. In case there is a decreasing trend in any of the metrics, the ELIXIR Hub will review both the content and the delivery (frequency, formats etc.) of the newsletter.

ELIXIR Informed - external stakeholder newsletter

ELIXIR's newsletter for external stakeholders - ELIXIR Informed - is sent out quarterly. It presents an overview of the past activities in the form of short stories linked to new content published on the ELIXIR website. All content published in the internal newsletter must be directly related to ELIXIR.

The goals of the Informed newsletter are to promote ELIXIR activities, inform external stakeholders about the latest development across the infrastructure, and drive more users to the ELIXIR website. The secondary goals are to increase participation (ie registration) at ELIXIR events and reach out to new users. Funders and policy-makers are active readers of the Informed newsletter, so showcasing impact and news on membership is also a priority.

These general goals translate into specific, measurable objectives for the Informed ELIXIR Newsletter:

- To increase Newsletter subscribers
- To increase the open rate of the newsletter
- To increase the click-through rate of the newsletter
- To increase registration at ELIXIR event through targeted email campaigns

The average growth of subscribers in the period January 2014 - April 2016 has been 10 new subscribers per month. The Informed newsletter will be promoted via the ELIXIR website and ELIXIR social media to attract new subscribers. The specific objective is to increase the growth rate by at least 50% by the end of 2016.

The average open rate of the ELIXIR external newsletter is now 29.1%, the click-through rate is 5.9%. The objective is to increase the open rate by at least 5% and the click-through rate by at least 2% by the end of 2016.

The Communications strategy workshop in December 2015 identified several aspects that can contribute to reaching the goals:

- **Improve the layout.** The newsletter is currently unstructured. Content structured by topics (e.g. by Platforms and Use Cases) will improve the click-through rate of the newsletter and drive more user to the ELIXIR website.
- **Increase the frequency.** The newsletter is currently sent out quarterly. More frequent periodicity (monthly or bi-monthly) will help in engaging new ELIXIR users and increase the number of subscribers
- **Develop new content.** New sections of the newsletter will include - profile presentations of ELIXIR Nodes, profile presentations of ELIXIR Community members and their role in ELIXIR, list of recent publications.

ELIXIR industry update

ELIXIR's newsletter for industry and SMEs brings news about latest developments and upcoming events relevant to industry.

The goal of the newsletter is to build and expand ELIXIR's industry stakeholders group and promote ELIXIR industry programme. The secondary goals are to increase participation (ie registration) at industry related events and reach out to new users.

The Industry update is now sent irregularly - approximately four times a year. Besides the Industry update issues, the subscribers also receive specific invitation to ELIXIR events (e.g. ELIXIR Innovation and SME's forums).

Print publications

The [ELIXIR Scientific Programme \(2014-2018\)](#) and [ELIXIR's Annual Reports](#) form the primary focus of ELIXIR's print publications and act as the official presentation of ELIXIR's objectives and review of annual activities.

Additional brochures and leaflets are used to present specific aspects of ELIXIR's activities in more digestible formats and to specific communities. In 2016, the goal is to develop a coherent set of printed materials for the Human Data Use case. This will serve as a model for developing new print materials for other user communities (Rare diseases, Marine metagenomics and Plants science).

Scientific publications

As a principle, any scientific or technical work to develop and improve ELIXIR infrastructure should be published in peer-reviewed scientific literature.

To help ensure awareness of ELIXIR's activities within the scientific community, ELIXIR encourages all members of the ELIXIR consortium to publish the outputs of their work in Open Access journals.

To support the process, ELIXIR Hub has a dedicated publication channel on the F1000Research channel, the ELIXIR Gateway: <http://f1000research.com/channels/elixir> . The ELIXIR channel is open to any member of the ELIXIR consortium.

ELIXIR Hub covers the article processing fees for all articles published in the channel.

Details on ELIXIR Publication policy and the ELIXIR f1000Research channel are available in [Annex VIII: ELIXIR Publication principles](#)

5. Communications assets

Graphic design - ELIXIR logo and other visual elements

ELIXIR Logo

ELIXIR has a distinct visual identity supported by the ELIXIR logo and additional visual elements. The ELIXIR logo has three different forms:

- The main ELIXIR logo
- ELIXIR Node logos
- Logos for ELIXIR Platforms and ELIXIR Services

Detailed guidelines for the use of ELIXIR logos are provided in Annex V. ELIXIR Branding guidelines. All ELIXIR Nodes logos and EXCELERATE logos are available via the intranet at: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-and-excelerate-logos>

The main ELIXIR logo should be used only for materials directly related to ELIXIR and when presenting ELIXIR as a whole. ELIXIR Nodes should always use their country's ELIXIR Node logo. However, to maximise the impact of ELIXIR brand, the main ELIXIR logo should not be used directly next to the ELIXIR Node logo, as it weakens the visual impact of both logos and may be confusing to users. If an event is co-organised by more than one ELIXIR Node or by the ELIXIR Hub and a Node or Nodes, the general ELIXIR logo should be used instead.

ELIXIR Platforms and ELIXIR Commissioned services can also use specific ELIXIR logos to brand their activities. These logos follow the same pattern as ELIXIR Nodes logo - the main ELIXIR logo is complemented by the name of the service or Platform (see Image 3). The Platforms and services logos will be provided upon request by ELIXIR Hub.

Image 2: Examples of ELIXIR Platform logo (left) and ELIXIR Service (right)

In specific cases the helix(swoosh) in the ELIXIR logo (Image 4) may be used in place of the full ELIXIR logo. Its use is however strictly limited to:

- Avatars (thumbnails) on social media platforms where the full ELIXIR logo would be too small (see Chapter 5: Social media)
- As a complement of existing logos of ELIXIR services to identify the service as ELIXIR services (Chapter 8: Promoting ELIXIR Services)

Image 3: ELIXIR Helix (swoosh)

EXCELERATE logo

The ELIXIR-EXCELERATE logo should be used in place of the ELIXIR logo for all activities and events carried out within the framework of the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE project. As per EC funding rules, the EXCELERATE logo should be always complemented by the flag of the European Union (Image 4).

Image 4: EXCELERATE logo with the EU flag

The acknowledgment of funding for ELIXIR-EXCELERATE activities is:

ELIXIR-EXCELERATE is funded by the European Commission within the Research Infrastructures programme of Horizon 2020, grant agreement number 676559.

It should be used on any print or online publications presenting the project and/or its results.

For activities only partly funded by ELIXIR-EXCELERATE, use ELIXIR logo together with the above acknowledgment of funding, specifying which parts were funded by ELIXIR-EXCELERATE (e.g. at the bottom of a publication or on the last slide).

Example:

*The Technical hackathon was supported by ELIXIR-EXCELERATE.
ELIXIR-EXCELERATE is funded by the European Commission within the
Research Infrastructures programme of Horizon 2020, grant agreement
number 676559.*

Other visual elements

The ELIXIR and ELIXIR-EXCELERATE logos are complemented by a set of icons representing individual Platforms and Use Cases of ELIXIR (Image 5).

Image 5: Icons representing ELIXIR platforms and use cases

The icons will be used as visual representation of the ELIXIR Platforms on the ELIXIR website and in ELIXIR publications. The icons are available via the internet, alongside the ELIXIR and EXCELERATE logos: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-and-excelerate-logos>

ELIXIR Presentations

To ensure consistency in presenting ELIXIR at conferences, workshops and other meetings, the ELIXIR Hub provides support to all members of ELIXIR community in preparing their slideshow presentations.

All presentations should be based on the main ELIXIR slide deck - a comprehensive collection of slides regularly updated and covering all aspect of ELIXIR activities. The ELIXIR Hub can also provide additional support in creating presentations targeted at a specific audience and topic.

All ELIXIR presentations should use the current ELIXIR template (for both slideshow and poster presentations).

The main ELIXIR slide deck and the presentation templates are available via the intranet at:

- <https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-presentations> (Slideshow)
- <https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-poster-template> (Poster)

ELIXIR Hub will also develop specific presentation content for ELIXIR Platforms and Use cases targeted to specific user communities. These specific presentations will introduce concrete activities and benefits of the ELIXIR Platforms and Use cases, addressing concrete issues faced by the respective scientific communities. The priority for 2016 is the Human Data Use Case.

Video

To support the communication of ELIXIR and its services, the ELIXIR Hub will produce a short video, featuring interviews with scientists and industry users. The goal of the video is to present the scope of ELIXIR, together with concrete ways of how the life science community can benefit from its services.

The video will be presented in the ELIXIR YouTube channel and on the ELIXIR website. It will be also distributed to ELIXIR Nodes to support their national communications activities, particularly during conferences and exhibitions.

The release of the video is planned for September 2016.

Events

ELIXIR events

Event communication activities will ensure that events organised by ELIXIR are promoted to the appropriate target audience and are properly branded. Upcoming events are be promoted on the ELIXIR website, in ELIXIR social media, in both internal and external Newsletters and through ELIXIR Nodes.

Detailed guidelines to organising ELIXIR events are available in Annex VI.

Presence at conferences

A programme of presentations of ELIXIR at international conferences is developed on a yearly basis and lists presentations of ELIXIR at conferences, seminars and other networking events.

The target audiences of ELIXIR presentations at conferences and other events are:

- Bioinformaticians
- Research funders

ELIXIR will regularly attend the major international conferences in bioinformatics and computational biology (ECCB, ISMB), but also domain specific conference relevant to ELIXIR Use cases (2016 NGS Conference in Barcelona, Spain, London Festival of Genomics).

ELIXIR Nodes (with support from the ELIXIR Hub) will focus on national bioinformatics meetings (e.g. Benelux Bioinformatics Conference, Annual Danish Bioinformatics Conference, BITS Annual meeting, Italy)

The focus of ELIXIR's conference presence in 2016 is on the European Conference on Computational Biology (ECCB) 2016, taking place on 3-7 September 2016 in the Hague, the Netherlands. ELIXIR has become the main organising sponsor of the conference and will have a dedicated Application track aimed at presenting a cross-section of ELIXIR activities and outcomes.

Detailed record of all presentation and dissemination activities:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1PiGJYu2zbo_yWCfZEogqIkJmRQQQHbR_ppeOYbV--wo/edit?usp=sharing

ELIXIR will produce a set of information materials and merchandise materials to engage with conference participants. The conference materials include:

- ELIXIR T-shirts
- Presentation slide sets
- Posters
- Other merchandise (power charger, stress ball, ELIXIR pins, etc.)

ELIXIR Nodes can already use ELIXIR pop-up banners, customised to their country. Contact your Head of Node in case you want to use the ELIXIR pop-up banner.

Example of the pop-up banner design: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/pull-banners-design>

Promoting ELIXIR events

The ELIXIR Hub, ELIXIR Platforms and use cases and ELIXIR Nodes organise various internal and external events; it is crucial that ELIXIR Hub and individual ELIXIR Nodes share and exchange information about their events and promote them on multiple platforms, without the need to re-publish ELIXIR events for each individual platform.

The central themes in promoting ELIXIR events is collection and distribution - the goal is that all events are published only once - on the website of the organising institutions. This event information is then collected in a central events repository and distributed to multiple websites via configurable widgets (Image 7).

Image 6: Exchange of events information in ELIXIR (Source: Gong C. Sharing events in ELIXIR [v1, not peer reviewed]. *F1000Research* 2016, 5(ELIXIR): 324 (poster) (doi: 10.7490/f1000research.11114.07.1)

This chapter sets out the scope for the different communications channels and platform within this system.

Events calendar on the ELIXIR website

www.elixir-europe.org/events

The events calendar on the ELIXIR website publishes only ELIXIR branded events - ELIXIR branded events organised by the ELIXIR Platforms or ELIXIR Nodes. If there is an event page already published on a website of an ELIXIR Node, the ELIXIR Hub event page will publish only basic information and link to the ELIXIR Node website.

Events organised by ELIXIR Nodes but not labelled as ELIXIR activities will not be published on the ELIXIR website. The events published on the ELIXIR website can be distributed to ELIXIR Nodes' websites, websites of ELIXIR services or any other website, using iAnn (<http://iann.pro/>).

Events on ELIXIR Nodes' websites

ELIXIR Nodes will publish their events on their own websites; these will be collected and then distributed to other ELIXIR websites.

TeSS portal

<https://tess.elixir-uk.org/events>

TeSS portal is the ELIXIR's Training portal. It collects and presents training events organised by the ELIXIR Hub, ELIXIR Nodes, ELIXIR Training platform and ELIXIR services (both organised within ELIXIR and outside ELIXIR). As such, the TeSS portal will provide calendar of all training courses related to ELIXIR (all training events - online and onsite - that meet the criteria for ELIXIR training as defined by the ELIXIR Training platform⁵⁷).

ELIXIR events portal

The ELIXIR events community portal will provide publishing platform for ELIXIR community members who don't have their own website or cannot - for various reasons - use their own platform. Those events will then be collected and distributed in the same way as events published on the ELIXIR Hub website or ELIXIR Nodes' websites.

ELIXIR internal newsletter (All at Nodes)

[Archive](#)

Events organised by ELIXIR Hub, ELIXIR Nodes or ELIXIR Platforms will be published in the internal newsletter once they have been published online. Each event will be included only once (in one issue of the newsletter), the newsletter will also include link to the full calendar of upcoming events (to TeSS portal for training events, to ELIXIR website for other ELIXIR events).

ELIXIR's external newsletter (ELIXIR Informed)

[Archive](#)

ELIXIR's external newsletter publishes information on major conferences and high-level policy events.

⁵ This document uses definition of ELIXIR Training, developed by ELIXIR Training platform as part of the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE work on ELIXIR Training quality and impact. The working version of the definition is at <http://bit.ly/1TZsUxe>

ELIXIR Industry update

ELIXIR Industry update publishes information on Innovation and SME events and other meetings run by ELIXIR of relevance to industry.

[Archive](#)

Evaluation and metrics

The evaluation of the Communications strategy will be carried out on a yearly basis, led by the ELIXIR Hub but with support from ELIXIR's communication experts. It will summarise and analyse the impact of each communication channel and – if necessary – adjust the strategy or individual communications actions.

ELIXIR communications metrics:

- Web traffic
- Performance of ELIXIR emails campaigns
- Twitter analytics (<https://analytics.twitter.com/user/ELIXIREurope/home>)
- Referral traffic
- Feedback from the ELIXIR user community - event evaluation surveys conducted after each event

The table below indicates the specific set of metrics used for each particular activity.

Table 5: ELIXIR Communications metrics

Communications channels	Web traffic	Newsletter metrics	Twitter analytics	Referral traffic	User feedback
Website	x	x			
Social media	x		x	x	x
Newsletters	x	x		x	
Videos	x				
Events		x		x	x

The specific targets for each of the metrics are:

- Web traffic - (more in website strategy)
 - User sessions per month:
 - Pageviews per month:
 - Bounce rate:
 - Average number of pages visited by user
 - Goal 1: users who visited at least 5 different pages
 - Goal 2: users who subscribed to ELIXIR Newsletter

- Social media:
 - Reach at least 2,000 followers by the end of 2016
 - Increase @mentions and retweets by 15% by the end of 2016
 - Improve referral traffic from Twitter by 20%
- Newsletter performance:
 - Increase the number of Newsletter subscribers by 30 % be the end of 2016
 - Increase Open rate of the newsletters by 5 %
 - Increase Click-through rate of the newsletters 2 %

6. Annexes

All annexes to the Communications strategy are available: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/documents/annexes-elixir-communications-strategy>

- Annex I: Web strategy⁶
- [Annex II: ELIXIR Branding guidelines](#) (pdf)
- [Annex III: Social media guidelines](#)
- [Annex IV: ELIXIR Writing style guide](#)
- [Annex V: Responding to requests from the press \(including crisis communication\)](#)
- [Annex VI: Guidelines and tips to organising ELIXIR workshops](#)
- [Annex VII: Promoting ELIXIR Services](#)
- [Annex VIII: ELIXIR Publication principles](#)

⁶ Currently being developed (May 2016)

The ELIXIR brand

guidelines and best practices

ELIXIR branding

ELIXIR connects life science laboratories throughout Europe so they can easily share and store research data.

ELIXIR's purpose is to help Europe's leading laboratories and data centres coordinate the collection, quality control and storage of experimental biological information, and to ensure that these data are integrated and made accessible to all facets of the scientific community. ELIXIR's member states are committed to the provision of open-access data in the interests of advancing research in the life sciences.

The ELIXIR brand

A brand is more than a logo: it is about perceptions and associations. ELIXIR's core principles spring from its goal to create a unified system through which biological data can be stored and made easily accessible.

What we do

ELIXIR ensures access to life science information by integrating data from a network of laboratories and data centres throughout Europe. It draws on the strengths of its diverse range of partners in order to facilitate discoveries that lead to improvements in human health, agriculture and the environment.

How we describe ourselves

ELIXIR's mission is to build a sustainable European infrastructure for biological information, supporting life science research and its translation to medicine and the environment, the bio-industries and society.

The word "ELIXIR" should always be written in all capital letters. An initial cap is used for the terms "Hub" and "Nodes".

Logos

ELIXIR has a distinct visual identity that can be achieved using one of three Logos:

- Main ELIXIR logo
- ELIXIR Node logo
- Endorsement logo.

The purpose of the logo

The purpose of a logo is to provide quick visual representation of a brand. The logo might be the first impression that people have of ELIXIR, so it is important that the logo has the highest possible impact and leaves an unforgettable impression.

How the Logos should be used

The main ELIXIR logo should be used only for materials relating to **all of ELIXIR**.

Normally, ELIXIR Nodes will make use of their country's ELIXIR Node logo. This logo might be used in, for example, slide and poster templates, letterhead or announcements.

In the interests of maximising the impact of the ELIXIR brand, the main ELIXIR logo must **not** be used directly next to the ELIXIR node logo. The overall effect of this juxtaposition is confusing and weakens the impact of both logos.

If an event is co-organised by more than one ELIXIR Node or by the Hub and a Node or Nodes, the general ELIXIR logo should suffice.

Endorsement Logos

The standard endorsement Logo ("Supported by") clarifies the nature of support given by the ELIXIR Node(s) towards an event or project. If the work or event has been funded directly by an ELIXIR Node, the endorsement logo may be used.

The endorsement logo has been specifically created for this purpose and no attempt should be made to recreate it in any way. Please do not alter or distort the letterforms, type style or visual relationship between the different elements. logo placement

The blank space around the logo is called a "protected area". The protected area is a buffer between the logo and other elements, for example paragraph text, pictures or other logos. It is important to have this blank area to preserve the authority and legality of endorsement logo.

About these guidelines

These guidelines are not static, and will develop as we learn and adapt to the changing environment in which we work and collaborate. Your feedback and input is always welcome and we encourage you to email your comments to the ELIXIR Directorate: ELIXIR-comms@ebi.ac.uk.

Help

If you have any questions about ELIXIR branding or how to apply these guidelines, please contact press@elixir-europe.org

Logo placement

How far should the logo be from the text?

The blank space around the logo is called the "protected area".

The protected area is a buffer between the logo and other elements, for example paragraph text, pictures or other logos.

The protected area is square, and corresponds to the distance from of the 'el' of the ELIXIR logo using the horizontal width for horizontal spacing and the vertical height for vertical spacing.

Some examples are shown here.

Logo colours

How should the different ELIXIR Node logos be used?

You should have four versions of your Node logo:

ELIXIR_[country]_white_background

Use this version when you are working with a white background.

ELIXIR_[country]_orange_background

Use this version when you have an orange background to work with (see Colours).

ELIXIR_[country]_colour_background

Use this version when you need to put the logo on any other colour background.

ELIXIR_[country]_endorsement

Only use the endorsement logo if the project or event has the financial support of your ELIXIR Node. Different versions are available for a range of backgrounds.

Using the logo against busy background images is not recommended.

If you have any questions about how to use ELIXIR logos, please contact: press@elixir-europe.org.

White background

Orange background

Other background colours (example)

Fonts

The main ELIXIR font is **Corbel**.

For continuous paragraph text we recommend an easily legible font size of 10-point, with a line spacing of 12-point.

Heading 1 should be four point sizes larger than the paragraph text. For example, if the main text is 12 point (with a 14-point leader) then Heading 1 should be 16 point (with an 18-point leader).

Heading 2 should be two point sizes larger than the paragraph text.

The smallest font size to be used in paragraph text is 8-point (with a 10-point leader), for example in a copyright line.

In slide presentations, the recommended minimum font size is 22 points.

Corbel regular (Header 1)

Corbel regular (Header 2)

(continuous text)

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890.,:;!%&/()=+-'"@

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Mauris mauris odio, eleifend in facilisis nec, eleifend in ante. Aliquam erat volutpat. Praesent eu lorem purus, nec tempus erat. Curabitur nec ante id elit lacinia luctus.

Corbel regular (Header 1)

Corbel regular (Header 2)

(continuous text)

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890.,:;!%&/()=+-'"@

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Mauris mauris odio, eleifend in facilisis nec, eleifend in ante. Aliquam erat volutpat. Praesent eu lorem purus, nec tempus erat. Curabitur nec ante id elit lacinia luctus.

Corbel regular (Header 1)

Corbel regular (Header 2)

(continuous text)

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890.,:;!%&/()=+-'"@

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Mauris mauris odio, eleifend in facilisis nec, eleifend in ante. Aliquam erat volutpat. Praesent eu lorem purus, nec tempus erat. Curabitur nec ante id elit lacinia luctus.

Corbel regular (Header 1)

Corbel regular (Header 2)

(continuous text)

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890.,:;!%&/()=+-'"@

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Mauris mauris odio, eleifend in facilisis nec, eleifend in ante. Aliquam erat volutpat. Praesent eu lorem purus, nec tempus erat. Curabitur nec ante id elit lacinia luctus.

Colours

ELIXIR's primary colours, derived from the logo, are orange and grey.

Two complementary colours, blue and green, are also available to use. Green, the fourth colour, is intended to be used as an accent colour rather than a feature colour.

Here we present colour profiles required for print (CMYK, corresponding to ink) and on-screen viewing (RGB, corresponding to light).

Special colours are also available for silkscreen printing, painting and plotter transparencies. Please contact press@elixir-europe.org for details.

We highly recommend using the ELIXIR colours at 100%. However, we recognise that on occasion you may need alternate shades of these colours in your design, for example when using a transparent layer. In such cases, please use the tints as specified below.

100% 70% 40% 20%

100% 70% 40% 20%

100% 70% 40% 20%

100% 70% 40% 20%

RGB colour mode (on screen)

Orange R 244 G 125 B 32
Grey R 77 G 72 B 72
Blue R 0 G 84 B 114
Green R 190 G 191 B 50

CMYK colour mode (printing)

Orange C 0 M 63 Y 100 K 0
Grey C 30 M 30 Y 30 K 70
Blue C 100 M 50 Y 30 K 30
Green C 30 M 14 Y 100 K 0

PMS coated colour mode

(custom professional printing)
Orange PMS 716
Grey PMS cool grey 11
Blue PMS 3025
Green PMS 583

Announcements

If you would like to publicise an ELIXIR Node event, we recommend following these basic guidelines in order to maximise the benefit of ELIXIR branding.

Web pages

Basics

Your event's web page should feature prominently the most crucial information:

- **Title**
- **Date**
- **Tagline**
- **Location and venue**
- **Overview**

Logo placement

Your ELIXIR Node logo should be placed at the bottom right of the page.

The distance between the logo and partner institute logos should be no closer than the width of the ELIXIR logo helix.

PDFs and html emails

When publicising your ELIXIR Node-affiliated event, you may wish to send an announcement to a broad audience in a formatted email or as a printed document/pdf.

When doing so, please use the ELIXIR font and colours. Include your ELIXIR Node logo with your contact information, and follow the placement guidelines as closely as possible.

Ensure that the recipient knows why they have been contacted, and has a mechanism for opting out of receiving such announcements.

We do not recommend issuing event announcements in the same manner as a press release, unless journalists are the primary audience for your ELIXIR-related event.

Help

If you have any questions about ELIXIR branding or how to apply these guidelines, please contact press@elixir-europe.org

ELIXIR Directorate

Tel. +44 (0)1223 494 665
E-mail press@elixir-europe.org
Website www.elixir-europe.org

Annex III: ELIXIR Social Media Guidelines

Social media refer to online tools that allow internet users to create and publish content. Many of these sites use personal profiles where users post information about themselves or they work, some of social media allow creating institutional profiles. The “social” in social media comes in as they enable and support sharing of content and user interaction.

Why ELIXIR social media

Social media are one of the most important tools in ELIXIR online communications - they enable ELIXIR to share what is happening in ELIXIR and help in getting feedback from ELIXIR stakeholders. This “conversation” - instant feedback from the the community of social media users is what makes social media so different from traditional forms of institutional communication.

ELIXIR maintains the ELIXIR twitter account as the main social media channel. This channel is complemented by a multitude of personal and institutional accounts managed by members of ELIXIR community. This guidelines aim to help those members create and maintain effective social media presence in support of ELIXIR.

Endorsements

There are two types of Twitter accounts related to ELIXIR: (1) official ELIXIR accounts, representing and managed by ELIXIR Hub, ELIXIR Nodes or ELIXIR services, and (2) Twitter accounts maintained by institutions or individuals - members of the ELIXIR community.

It should be clear to users whether the account and its content is an official ELIXIR channel (set up by ELIXIR Nodes or ELIXIR services), or whether it is a personal/institutional account, run outside ELIXIR.

For official accounts, the ELIXIR logo should be used for the avatar picture, the account name should follow the same pattern:

- ELIXIR [country] for ELIXIR Nodes (e.g. ELIXIR Italy, ELIXIR UK, ELIXIR Norway)
- ELIXIR [service] for ELIXIR services (e.g. ELIXIR TeSS)

For institutions acting as an ELIXIR Node (e.g. DTL in the Netherlands, SIB in Switzerland), their ELIXIR affiliation can be mentioned in the account description. ELIXIR Nodes are also encouraged to add the ELIXIR helix to their avatar picture (see image 1 below).

Image 1: Twitter avatar for official ELIXIR account

The use of an ELIXIR pin is also recommended for personal accounts of members of the ELIXIR community (see image 2 below). Twitter users can add the ELIXIR helix to their avatars via: <http://twibbon.com/Support/elixir-4>.

Image 2: Twitter avatars with ELIXIR helix (left - personal, right - institutional)

However, creating ‘hybrid’ accounts (for example personal profiles with ELIXIR in their name or ELIXIR logo in the avatar picture) should be avoided, as they are likely to cause confusion and risk editorial problems.

Retweets, hashtags and interactions

Members of the ELIXIR community are encouraged to retweet, like or comment on posts by official ELIXIR accounts.

To cite ELIXIR on Twitter, use the ELIXIR Hub Twitter handle: @ELIXIREurope. When posting about specific activities or events, always cite the ELIXIR Node or service (or ELIXIR Hub), that leads the work (as organiser, author, coordinator); the list of official Twitter accounts is in Annex VII and will be updated regularly.

Use hashtags for specific events, or activities. Major events organised by ELIXIR should have a specific hashtag to allow interaction between the event participants and to promote the event to the broader community. Don't use #ELIXIR hashtag, it is too generic and likely to connect your tweet with non-ELIXIR content. For general posts about ELIXIR, use the ELIXIR Twitter handle instead (@ELIXIREurope).

Best practices guidelines and practical tips for setting up and running an ELIXIR Twitter account are available in Annex VII: ELIXIR Social Media guidelines.

Content

ELIXIR posts news, events and jobs to Twitter and retweets posts from ELIXIR Nodes, ELIXIR services and key thought-leaders from within the community. Occasionally, ELIXIR shares posts from collaborators and partners.

As a general rule, all posts should link to information that is useful and freely available to users: training, job opportunities, reports, news stories, research papers and outcomes of technical activities. Posts from ELIXIR-related accounts should not contain views which would damage ELIXIR's reputation or relations with key partners.

Practical tips and guidelines for managing Social media accounts

Although many of the points below are general enough to apply to any social media platforms, it was written mainly with Twitter in mind.

Before you start

Before you start a new social media account, think about the following:

- Do you really need a separate account?

Social media platforms are typically seen as 'easy' and 'free', but efficient social media presence requires dedicated time and effort.

- Do you have the time to post regularly and keep you account updated?
- Do you have enough unique content to share?
- What do you want to achieve with your account, what is your target audience?
- What/who will your social media represent (you, your institution, team, your ELIXIR Node, the service you are part of)?
- Will your social media mention and promote ELIXIR and / or its services?

In some cases, using existing social media accounts (that of your institutions or your ELIXIR Node), may be more efficient than creating a new account and building your audience from scratch. This is especially true for EU projects - they typically last three or four years. Be aware that your new social media account will not bring direct benefit in the first months of your social media activity. It usually takes at least a couple of months (but often more than a year) of dedicated effort for a new social media account to become a communications asset - new accounts need to attract their audience and gain reputation.

Getting ready

- If you decide to create social media account and plan to actively promote ELIXIR, get in touch with Premysl or the Communications Officer in your Node. We may provide you further practical support in setting up the account and extend your reach.

The next steps in starting your social media accounts:

- Get it approved.
If you are creating a social media account for your Node or your service, make sure your senior manager knows about it and approves it.
- Define your goals.
Think about what you want to achieve with your account. This will help in creating relevant content and understand how to best reach your audience.
- Find the right people.
Appoint a coordinator - a primary person responsible for updating and monitoring your site. Ensure they have the time to check in on the site at least once a day. This may not need to take up a significant amount of time, but successful social media sites are updated frequently, enable easy engagement with viewers and adjust in response to timely events and problems.
- Listen.
Before getting started observe activity on the site, learn from the activities of established brands and from the conversations and interactions on the site. All social media platforms have their own standards, styles and expectations. By consuming content on social media before producing it, you will learn how these communities work, what content is of most interest, what hashtags are regularly used in your community etc.. Follow relevant groups and people.
- Create your profile.
Create a profile name - short and concise - that clearly and concisely identifies your programme. Do not identify yourself simply as ELIXIR, do not use the ELIXIR logo as the only visual element of your profile. The main title/your account name should not include 'ELIXIR', unless it is an official account of an ELIXIR Node.
Add your ELIXIR affiliation to the About/Bio section. You can use the ELIXIR

helix (swoosh) as part of your profile picture to highlight your ELIXIR affiliation (An easy way to do it is via twibbon at: <http://twibbon.com/Support/elixir-4>).

Contact Premysl (premysl.velek@elixir-europe.org) if you need support in creating visuals for your social media site (profile picture, banners, etc.). Co

- Launch.

Use traditional means - email lists, printed materials and your website, to notify your potential audiences that you have a social media presence. Also, notify others with social media presences and similar interests that your site is live – one of the best ways to do this is by linking to these sites from yours and mentioning them in your posts. Include easy-to-find links to your social media presence on your website.

- Monitor and adjust.

Once your site online, you will find some of your posts quickly become popular, some less so and some are simply ignored. There are plenty of media tools that let you analyse your posts' performance and track interactions with your audience. The most common for Twitter are:

- Tweetdeck: <http://tweetdeck.twitter.com>
- Hootsuite: <https://hootsuite.com/>
- Twitter analytics: <https://analytics.twitter.com>
- Klout: <https://klout.com>
- Buffer: <http://buffer.com/>

Ten simple rules for promoting ELIXIR on twitter

1. Post regularly - an outdated account with the last post from two years ago may be damaging to your (and ELIXIR's) reputation.
2. Avoid jargon. Keep your language plain and simple.
3. Include clear call to action - a link to your website, link to ELIXIR's website.
4. Cite, link and retweet ELIXIR whenever possible.
5. Leave political positioning to leadership.

6. Always respond to questions and comments, but don't engage in twitter fights. Treat your audience respectfully. If you receive offensive comments, contact your communications officer or Premysl premysl.velek@elixir-europe.org.
7. Never share ELIXIR's or your institution's internal information.
8. Use the 80/20 principle. 80% of your activities should be interactions with your followers - retweets, replies and likes. 20% should be your own tweets.
9. Post pictures. Photos from events, logos, simple charts and infographics will make your tweets stand out.
10. Make use of hashtags, some of the commonly used hashtags for bioinformatics: `#bioinformatics`, `#usegalaxy`, `#datamanagement`, `#NGS`, `#genomics`, `#bigdata`

Annex IV: ELIXIR Style guide

Any text presenting ELIXIR or ELIXIR service becomes part of ELIXIR public face. This style guide is the primary reference tool for all members of ELIXIR community - ELIXIR Hub and ELIXIR Node staff, external suppliers and partners. It outlines the English standards for all ELIXIR communications.

Writing for the web

Web content in general requires a direct, clear writing style. A well-structured and concise web article allows readers to scan it – to look for and pick out individual keywords while skipping over large parts of the text not immediately relevant to their goals.

A scannable text:

- Is structured into short segments, labelled by meaningful headings and sub-headings
- Contains highlighted keywords (e.g. links)
- Uses bullet points
- Gets straight to the point without long introductions or “welcome” messages
- Uses the inverted pyramid style – the most important information (the conclusion, main objectives etc.) is placed at the very beginning, followed by supporting information and background
- Is significantly shorter than a text for a print publication

Good writing should be clear and concise:

- Avoid longer words or phrases where shorter ones would do (*start vs. commence*)
- Keep sentences and paragraphs short
- Prefer active to passive sentences. Instead of *Two new Implementations studies are being launched by ELIXIR*, say *ELIXIR is launching two new Implementations studies*
- Use simple English. Remember that people from all over the world read the website, and English may be their second or third language.
- Check the readability of your text with online tools like at online-utility.org and read-able.com.

- Proofread. Read the whole thing back to yourself, ask your colleagues to read your writing.

See the Plain English guidelines for more practical tips to improve the clarity of your writing:

<http://www.plainenglish.co.uk/files/howto.pdf>

Other practical tips for web content:

- Links should be descriptive.
 - Not very good: *Click [here](#) to visit the ELIXIR website say*
 - Better: *Visit [the ELIXIR website](#).*
- Keywords (words or phrases describing the content) placed in the headings and in the first few paragraphs help search engines better index your page
- Pages with "under construction" or "more information coming soon" messages may discourage visitors from coming back. A new content should not be published until it is complete.
- Justified text and centered headings make online reading more difficult
- Links to other content (both within and outside the portal) in formats other than an internet page (pdf files, videos, sound files etc.) should be labeled accordingly.

Style guide

ELIXIR specific terms

- ELIXIR - always capitalised, the only exception is the ELIXIR logo
- ELIXIR-EXCELERATE - EXCELERATE is always capitalised and never stands alone (without ELIXIR)
- ELIXIR Node, ELIXIR Platforms - Node and Platforms are capitalised
- ELIXIR Use cases
 - For names of ELIXIR Use cases use sentence case: Marine metagenomics, Human data, Rare diseases
- ELIXIR Members (Capital M)
- ELIXIR Board

- ELIXIR Technical Coordinators' Group
- ELIXIR Training Coordinators' Group
- Heads of Node (Node in singular, Heads in plural when referring to all Heads of Node)

Abbreviations and acronyms

- Write abbreviations and contractions in full when you first mention them, e.g. European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL).
- In general, don't use a full point or spaces in upper case abbreviations, e.g. Mrs FM Barker not Mrs F. M. Barker, NATO not 'N.A.T.O.'.
- Don't use the full point for contractions, e.g. Mr nor Mr., Dr not Dr. But Prof. not Prof
- Avoid using ELIXIR specific acronyms (HoN, TrCG, WP6, etc.) in public websites and documents.

Dates

- Use 26 May 2016, 26 May or May 2016 (not May 26 2012, 26th May or 26/05/2012).

Emails

- Give 'Email' a capital 'E' only when it starts a sentence or when it is mentioned in an address block
- Write email addresses in lowercase, e.g. fred.bloggs@elixir-europe.org rather than Fred.Bloggs@elixir-europe.org.
- Don't use a hyphen (i.e. email, not e-mail).

Headlines

- Make the headlines as informative as possible, e.g. *Two vacancies at ELIXIR Hub* rather than *Two job vacancies*.
- Keep them as short as you can whilst still being informative. If possible, include an active verb.

Names

- First and last names should be used when mentioned for the first time. After that only first names should be used.

Programme

- Program is for computer programs. Programme is for conference programmes.

Spelling

- UK spelling is preferred. Trade names and name of a corporate bodies or firms should be reproduced without change (e.g. CSC - Center for Science)

As a reference guide for spelling and linguistic convention, use the *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, published by the European Commission, Translation DG

(http://ec.europa.eu/translation/english/guidelines/documents/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf)

Time

- Use 24-hour clock rather than 12-hour clock (14.10 not 2.10pm).
- For a period of time, use 16-16.30, rather than 16.00-16.30.
- Always include time zone (GMT, BST, CEST)

Annex V: Responding to requests from the press (including crisis communication)

This policy sets out the process to follow if partners are contacted by the press and asked for official information or interviews about ELIXIR.

Background

As ELIXIR's profile grows there is likely to be more and more interest from national and European science press about the operational developments of ELIXIR. Overall this is a welcome development and is testament to the progress being made and the high-profile grant that has been awarded. However, it is also possible that, depending on the publication, some coverage will contain a negative focus or inaccurate information.

Given the size of ELIXIR - in terms of number of partners and the breadth of activities - it is important that journalists and press contacts are given correct, factual information that is not open to false interpretation in anyway. For this reason, if you are contacted spontaneously by the press or a journalist asking for official information, please follow the steps below:

Steps to follow

- Refer any journalists to contact the ELIXIR Hub (contact details below)
- Take the journalist's and publication's name and inform the Hub in parallel of the contact

ELIXIR contacts:

Andrew Smith

External Relations Manager, ELIXIR

andrew.smith@elixir-europe.org

+44 (0) 1223 494635

Premysl Velek

Communications and Outreach Officer, ELIXIR

premysl.velek@elixir-europe.org

+44 (0) 1223 494235

Full ELIXIR Hub staff details here: <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about/elixir-hub>

Crisis Communications plan

The Crisis communication plan aims to protect or defend ELIXIR as an organisation when facing a public challenge to its reputation.

Notification

A crisis can be defined as an unexpected event or situation that has the potential to damage ELIXIR's reputation. In such situations ELIXIR Director, ELIXIR External Manager and ELIXIR Communications Officer should be notified immediately. All media and public inquiries should be referred to ELIXIR Hub for comment.

Assessment

ELIXIR Hub will assess the situation and decide on the following questions:

- What is the situation? What will happen next?
- Who on staff needs to be involved?
- What immediate steps need to be taken?
- What is known and who already knows it?
- Who will be affected?
- What can and cannot be said?
- How will response be communicated? This usually include: news release on ELIXIR website and social media, newsletter article, one-on-one meetings, media release; media conference (for high urgency and high level issues)
- Who will be contacted? (Heads on Nodes, ELIXIR Board, Funders, press, ...)

Developing Key Messages

ELIXIR hub will develop factual, responsive messages. These messages should be prepared for media inquires, member updates, and proactive phone calls to critical audiences if necessary and relevant.

The message should answer questions that are likely be asked and may include additional materials such as a fact sheet, background, web site resources, FAQs, etc.

Guidelines and tips for workshops

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[Workshop guidelines](#)

[Agenda](#)

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Introduction

These guidelines contain things to consider when planning an ELIXIR-funded workshop to ensure it is as effective as possible and delivers concrete outcomes for organisers and participants.

For workshops funded through H2020 grants (e.g. ELIXIR-EXCELERATE) there are **important additional requirements from the EC** (outlined below).

Workshop guidelines

Agenda

- include dates, times, venue and topics (if there are changes in location - e.g. different rooms - between different agenda items, include that information as well!)
- circulate in advance
- allow attendees to submit agenda items - this can easily be achieved by preparing the agenda in Google documents

- Strive to make the agenda action-oriented - consider sharing information on agenda topics (background, reading material, proposed solutions/decisions) in advance

Attendees

- be clear on who should and should not be attending the workshop (who is the target audience?)
- consider workshop size
 - too small, inadequate representation from the community
 - too large, can impede workshop objectives being reached

Carbon footprint

- to minimise the environmental impact of physical meetings, a carbon emission reduction policy should be followed
- consider whether a physical meeting is essential? If not, the many telepresence technologies can be made use of to hold a remote meeting.
- where possible, hold face-to-face meetings back-to-back to minimise travel.

Communication

- if the workshops aims to attract external audience, think about how you want to promote and communicate the event.
- All workshops should be published on the ELIXIR website:
<https://www.elixir-europe.org/events>. Create the workshop page at:
<https://www.elixir-europe.org/node/add/events> (you have to be logged in!). Think about who can access the event page (everybody, only partners and colleagues, ...). For more details on how to use the website, see [link to the guidelines on how to use the ELIXIR intranet - PV to produce].
- ensure all relevant [ELIXIR platforms and communities](#) are informed about the workshop
- Consider other venues and channels to promote your event, eg. social media. On twitter, use the appropriate hashtags referring to ELIXIR platforms (#ELIXIR_training, #ELIXIR_data, #ELIXIR_data, ...) . For large events (more than 30-40 participants), consider having a specific hashtag related to the event and let the participants know.
- Consider taking photos during the event
- Collect the slides from the speakers and consider making them available online.
- After the event publish a news article about the event and its main outcomes (e.g. in the ELIXIR weekly updates).
- Reports and main outcomes should also be [disseminated via the relevant mailing lists](#).

Impact

- Strive to capture outcomes in a formal publication, white paper or report
- “living document” - a Google doc that is open for all attendees to contribute to before/during/after workshop - finalise post workshop to add to a useful record of the workshop; assign at least one person who has primary responsibility for adding content to/editing the living document (otherwise it can get very chaotic)
- Conduct feedback survey
- Hold an internal “post mortem”: what worked, what didn’t work, what were the challenges, did the workshop fulfil its purpose, what would have made it better, was it the right workshop format? etc.

Software & tools

- delegate registration
 - [Eventbrite](#) - good for large conference type events, automatic email confirmations, able to take payments
 - [Google forms](#) - free, easy and quick to set-up, no automatic email confirmations
 - [Ungerboeck Software](#) - professional event management software, associated fee, good when payments need to be taken

Speaker diversity

- strive for diversity of speakers to ensure all areas of the field under discussion are represented - for example, speakers from other relevant ELIXIR Nodes, representatives from the broader community, i.e. BMS RI, e-Infrastructures
- consider gender balance and equal opportunities before inviting speakers - have you considered all of the possible speakers/contributors? (Also see EC [guidelines](#))

Scheduling

- As soon as you are thinking about organising a workshop - either in the wider ELIXIR context or for EXCELERATE - make sure you check with the Hub/the ELIXIR events calendar and/or consult the EXCELERATE project calendar to ensure proper alignment and scheduling of activities
- Once the date has been set, make sure this is added to the ELIXIR events calendar or EXCELERATE project calendar, as appropriate

Structure

- Review presentations/lightning talks/breakout sessions etc to ensure productive discussions and tangible outcomes
- Interactive sessions and audience participation are a great way to get results - but it is extremely important that you think about how to guide or drive these sessions, and how the results will be captured (some very [useful tips on interactive workshops](#) can be found here). At a minimum, provide a short explanatory paragraph or presentation of the question(s) to be discussed, and make sure you have someone who takes notes plus someone who leads the group discussion
- is it a stand alone workshop or will there be a follow-up workshop/is it part of a workshop series or bigger effort?

Workshop outline

- the below outline may be helpful when planning a workshop
- the outline should be made visible on a website
 - workshop overview - brief background to the workshop
 - audience - who should/not be attending
 - workshop aims/objectives - specific/measurable
 - background - pre-reading or pre-work (as appropriate)
 - programme - detailed agenda

Requirements for workshops run as part of European Commission-funded projects

There are additional formal requirements for organising workshops within the EXCELERATE project or any other European Commission-funded project, taking into account rules on how funding can be used and what is formally required (for cost related questions, see the [“European Commission funding rules in a nutshell”](#) document), and for any remaining questions, please [contact project management](#).

Venue and meals

Venue (i.e. meeting room) and meals should be provided from project funds by the workshop organiser. In some cases, these might be specified as “workshop costs” in the Description of Action (DoA = Part B of the Grant Agreement, a.k.a. the proposal) and would be budgeted under “other direct costs”.

Please note that EC funding rules only allow costs for **meals that are needed during working meetings**, i.e. a dinner would have to be a ‘working dinner’ to be eligible for reimbursement by the Commission. If you are organising such a working dinner it is advisable to have an agenda that can be presented if the project costs are audited. (Please note that, in some cases, national rules or the rules of your own organisation may be more restrictive - please check with your administration.)

Travel and accommodation

Travel and accommodation (hotel rooms) for **workshop attendees, if they are employees of an organisation that is funded within EXCELERATE**, must be covered by their home organisation (normally, each organisation that gets funding from EXCELERATE would have included a certain amount for “travel” to attend workshops, conferences etc. in their budget under “other direct costs”).

Travel and accommodation for **external experts - individuals from organisations that are not part of and funded by EXCELERATE** - is NOT eligible for reimbursement by the host/workshop organiser (and, consequently, the European Commission) UNLESS the participation of experts is foreseen in the DoA. If, during project implementation, it turns out that the contribution of external experts to the work of the project is needed, please [contact project management](#) right away so we can try to get advance approval from the European Commission’s Project Officer in charge of the project. In this case, a good justification will be needed, and approval is not guaranteed!

Registration fees

Registration fees should normally NOT be taken as part of an EC funded project as such fees would be considered a project INCOME that would be SUBTRACTED from the eligible costs to be reimbursed by the Commission. In other words, if the event is funded through the project, it should be

fully funded through the project - charging fees is actually a disadvantage for the organiser in terms of covering the costs!

Underbudgeted?...

If necessary it is possible to shift budget between different cost categories or tasks/deliverables within the same work package (if you have planned in such detail at the proposal stage) to accomplish the tasks described in the DoA. However, this must be within reasonable limits – if there is a significant change between cost categories, please [contact project management](#) in advance so we can examine and track such shifts and the overall budget use. (Note that shifts between different work packages are more complicated and would need discussion and preparation well in advance!).

Documentation

For each workshop, it is extremely important that you provide:

- an **agenda** with dates, times, venue and topics
- a **list of participants** with signatures by the attendees
- **minutes or a report**, or at least a list of outcomes and action items

Ideally, the minutes should fulfil their intended purpose, i.e.

- a list of action items for shorter meetings where only details of how to implement something are discussed
- a more detailed workshop report for a longer meeting, possibly with a larger number of attendees, where strategies or plans are developed.

Note that also for the second type of minutes, a list of action items can be very helpful if it is possible to define specific issues and next steps.

Who pays what?

Workshop costs and who pays: Venue costs

Workshop costs and who pays: Travel costs

Related documents

[Annex 1: Venue suggestions](#)

[Annex 2: Event registration](#)

[Annex 3: "European Commission funding rules in a nutshell"](#)

Promoting ELIXIR Services

ELIXIR Services are the 'core business' of ELIXIR. As such, the effective communication of what services ELIXIR offers and how users can benefit from them is one of the central parts of ELIXIR's Communication strategy.

The strategy of promoting ELIXIR services was discussed in the ELIXIR Technical Coordinators' Group at the ELIXIR All Hands meeting in March 2016 in Barcelona. The group proposed a number of measures to promote ELIXIR services; this document summarises the outcomes of the meeting and proposes an action plan for implementing the proposed measures.

What are ELIXIR Services - definitions

All services included in ELIXIR Nodes' Service Delivery Plans are considered ELIXIR Services. In addition, there will be a limited number ELIXIR Commissioned Services, funded through the ELIXIR Hub budget each year, and ELIXIR Core Resources, for which the metrics are currently being developed within ELIXIR-EXCELERATE Work Package 3. Both Commissioned Services and Core Resources will have a distinctive branding. As the criteria for ELIXIR Commissioned Services and Core Resources are yet to be developed, this chapter provides general guidelines applicable to all existing and future ELIXIR services, rather than specific strategy for different types of ELIXIR services.

ELIXIR services on the ELIXIR website - Service summary pages

Presentation of ELIXIR services should be one of the central parts of the ELIXIR website, as the services are the main offering to the life science community. The presentation will be user-centred: it will focus on the concrete problems life science researchers face and how ELIXIR services can help in solving them.

Work is currently underway in the ELIXIR Hub to develop an inventory of all ELIXIR Services. The inventory will provide the necessary information for the service summary pages.

On the website, the services will be aligned with the ELIXIR Platforms and Use Cases, according to their type (e.g. data deposition, data access, cloud computing, interoperability). Each service (or a group of similar services) will then be presented on a dedicated page in a concise and visually appealing manner. The summary pages will focus on:

- Who are the target groups for the services (data generators, SME/Pharma informaticians, data providers, bioinformaticians)
- What challenges the service addresses
- What solutions these services offer and how end users benefit from it

The page will also include information about the operators and developers of the service, with contact details, and about any relevant training materials and training courses.

For 2016, the priority for developing the summary pages is given to cloud services.

Success stories

For selected services, in addition to summary pages we will develop success stories to showcase how the services helped solve concrete problems by concrete researchers. These stories will demonstrate how the services can be used in life science research and/or industry, helping in real life situations. They will also become testimonials for the ELIXIR Service and for ELIXIR as such.

The success stories will focus on unique value of the service, and on the added value of the service as part of ELIXIR. Each success story will follow the three step structure:

Challenge:

- What was the challenge faced by the user?
- Why was it important for the user to solve the problem?

Solution:

- How did the service or tool solve the problem?
- Why it was the best solution?

Outcomes:

- Statistics of performance before and after using the ELIXIR Service
- How did the user save time or improve efficiency?
- Why does this matter?
- What is the added value of ELIXIR in this concrete solution
- What should other users with similar problems do to benefit from the service (Call to Action)

The above model example outlines how the success stories will be structured. However, only a part of the question will be relevant to particular resources, so the model structure will always need to be adjusted to individual cases.

Similarly to the Summary pages, in 2016 ELIXIR Hub will focus on developing success stories for cloud computing services.

Branding ELIXIR services

In most cases services run by partners already have their own established visual identity. To visually identify those services as being part of ELIXIR, the ELIXIR helix (swoosh, Image 4) can be incorporated into the existing logo if desired. The full ELIXIR logo (for Commissioned and Core Resources), or ELIXIR Node logo (for ELIXIR Services) should be used whenever required.

The ELIXIR logo or ELIXIR Node logo may additionally be displayed on the website of the service or resource and this is encouraged as a minimum.

The standard boilerplate text for ELIXIR (see Chapter 2: ELIXIR Communications architecture) should also be published (typically in the “About” page of the Service website), alongside the presentation of the service itself and the service operator (the ELIXIR Node).

The benefits of ELIXIR Services for users will differ for each individual services. However, the main added value of being part of ELIXIR is that they are stable, reliable and can be built on. In this respect, the ELIXIR logo takes the role of a seal of quality; the messages developed for each individual service should highlight this aspect.

Referencing and acknowledgement

ELIXIR services may provide guidelines how researchers should reference their services in their publications and presentations. Example of such acknowledgement:

We acknowledge [Name of the service], part of ELIXIR (part of ELIXIR [Country] Node), for providing us access to the resource [Tool, Database, Standard, Compute system name] based in [country] at [site].

Where technical support has been received, the following additional text should also be used:

“The support of [name of person(s)] from [organisation name], [ELIXIR Node name] to the technical work is gratefully acknowledged.”

ELIXIR Publications Principles

Principles to follow

- Wherever possible, work to develop and improve the ELIXIR research infrastructure is published in peer-reviewed scientific literature;
- To help ensure awareness of ELIXIR's activities within the scientific community, ELIXIR encourages partners to publish the outputs of their work in Open Access journals. Open publishing and community journals are ideal to engage the community and stimulate an active discussion on proposed solutions.
- The [ELIXIR Reports](#), the ELIXIR F1000Research channel provides an option for open access, open peer-review publication. ELIXIR Hub covers article processing charges for ELIXIR related papers published in this channel;
- The existence of ELIXIR F1000R channel does not preclude arrangements and future agreements with further bioinformatics community journals;
- For avoidance of doubt: the corresponding author always decides on the most appropriate channel for publication;
- When the work behind the publication has received grant funding, authors should properly acknowledge the source of this funding:

- For activities funded by the ELIXIR Hub (e.g. Implementation Studies, ELIXIR sponsored workshops) please use the following acknowledgement:

This work was funded by ELIXIR, the research infrastructure for life-science data.

- For activities funded by EC grants,, the Grant Agreement provides specific instructions on how the funding must be acknowledged - e.g. for EXCELERATE, you have to include the following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 676559.

For all other grants, please refer to the instructions for acknowledgement of the respective funder.

- For position papers, working papers or any documents not suitable for peer-review use a service that can generate a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). [Zenodo](#) is free, you can sign in with a GitHub or ORCID account, and each document is given a DOI. You can also create community collections.

ELIXIR *F1000Research* Gateway

<http://f1000research.com/channels/elixir/>

F1000Research is an open-science publishing platform for life scientists that offers immediate open access publication and transparent post-publication peer review by invited referees, and full data deposition and sharing. F1000Research accepts all scientifically sound articles, including single findings, case reports, protocols, replications, null/negative results, and more traditional articles.

The ELIXIR Gateway on F1000Research is the official platform for scientific publications and presents all publications output from across ELIXIR. ELIXIR Nodes are strongly encouraged to publish reports and results from their activities in this channel, including outputs from ELIXIR-EXCELERATE, Implementation studies and from national projects related to ELIXIR.

The scope of the ELIXIR Gateway:

- Papers, slides and posters that describe ELIXIR services, technology developments, and architecture overviews
- Surveys, best practice recommendations and workshop outcomes
- Submissions that describe development and implementation of standards and collaborative efforts
- ELIXIR projects will also publish reports on progress and deliverables through the gateway

The ELIXIR Gateway has two channels:

- **ELIXIR Reports** channel publishes outputs from ELIXIR's technical activities, ELIXIR strategy documents and other articles describing ELIXIR infrastructure and its services, including ELIXIR implementation studies and EXCELERATE project reports.
- **Posters and Slides** channel publishes scientific posters, slideshow presentations and other materials to present the outcomes and activities of ELIXIR and its projects.

ELIXIR Gateway Advisory Board

The ELIXIR Gateway is managed by the ELIXIR Editorial Board. The Board members - representatives of the ELIXIR Hub and the ELIXIR Nodes - will accept submissions based on the agreed scope for the channel and ensure that the articles published in the ELIXIR channels are relevant to the ELIXIR community. However, once an article is accepted for submission to the channel the Board will not interfere in the open review process provided by F1000Research.

Members of the ELIXIR Gateway Advisory Board

- Niklas Blomberg, ELIXIR Director
- Arlindo Oliveira, Head of Node, ELIXIR Portugal
- Barend Mons, Head of Node, ELIXIR Netherlands
- Bengt Persson, Head of Node, ELIXIR Sweden
- Inge Jonassen, Head of Node, ELIXIR Norway

To encourage submissions from across ELIXIR, ELIXIR Hub will cover the Application Processing Fees for all submissions accepted by the ELIXIR Editorial Board.